

Connecting the dots: The role of internationally mobile scientists in linking non-mobile with foreign scientists

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Abstract

Internationally mobile scientists meet foreign scientists and become knowledge carriers. The benefits of international mobility might extend to non-mobile colleagues who collaborate with mobile scientists. This paper investigates the role played by Brazilian and Colombian mobile scientists in connecting non-mobile scientists with foreign ones. We combine data from CVs, scholarship programs, and publications in OpenAlex. We analyze a sample covering approximately 70% of scientists in both countries and their co-authorship networks between 1990-2021, combining panel estimations and a DiD event study. We find that non-mobile scientists who co-author with mobile scientists co-author have more publications with foreign scientists. The number of foreign collaborations increases with the number of mobile scientists with whom they interact, partly because the effect of collaborating with each mobile scientist is short-lived. Results also suggest that mobile scientists who return to their home countries after Ph.D. are the least effective in creating connections with foreign scientists. Our contribution relates to the insights on the spillover generated by mobility experiences in connecting non-mobile with foreign scientists. Our results indicate a need to increase brain gain and reduce brain drain by using flexible conditions to return to home countries and improving the links between mobile and non-mobile scientists.

Introduction

In the last decades, governments in high- and low-income countries have long been promoting policies to support the training of students and scientists abroad (Baruffaldi, Marino, & Visentin, 2020; Jonkers & Tijssen, 2008). Academic and policy actors worldwide recognize the role of international mobility in fostering knowledge creation and diffusion, which contribute to economic growth (Baruffaldi & Landoni, 2012; Cañibano, 2017; OECD, 2018). Internationally mobile scientists and students who spend time abroad absorb tacit knowledge through face-to-face interactions, access scientific infrastructures, and expand their social capital (Bozeman, Dietz, & Gaughan, 2001). For internationally mobile scientists, periods abroad improve their research productivity (Netz, Hampel, & Aman, 2020). For the countries of origin of those mobile scientists, benefits arise when sojourners return, carrying with them knowledge that can be applied both to research on local socio-economic needs and training new students and scientists (Cañibano, 2017; Trippl, 2013).

Mobile scientists may also contribute to the internationalization of their home scientific systems by connecting the local scientific community to the global community (Velema, 2012). Empirical studies demonstrate that time spent abroad to do research leads internationally mobile scientists (henceforth “mobile scientists”) to have larger international co-authorship networks than scientists who spend their careers in their home countries (henceforth “non-mobile scientists”) (Aykaç, 2021; Cao, Baas, Wagner, & Jonkers, 2020; Gibson & McKenzie, 2014; Jonkers & Cruz-Castro, 2013). Many studies suggest that, given their larger stock of international co-authors, mobile scientists may benefit non-mobile scientists from their country of origin by connecting them to foreign scientists. Nonetheless, these studies rarely analyze whether and how non-mobile scientists establish collaboration with foreign scientists through mobile scientists. As such, the literature is unclear on the extent to which mobile scientists are an essential resource for non-mobile scientists to form foreign ties.

This paper addresses this gap by investigating how much collaboration with mobile scientists affects the probability that a non-mobile scientist collaborates with foreign scientists located abroad. Specifically, we examine whether co-authoring with mobile scientists increases the number of publications with foreign scientists. We investigate the extensive and intensive margin, distinguishing between science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) and social science and humanities (SSH). Because mobility patterns influence both the likelihood that non-mobile scientists form ties with mobile scientists, and the foreign networks of the mobile scientists, we distinguish three types of mobile scientists: diaspora (never return to the country of origin), returnees (return indefinitely to the country of origin), and intermittent (work for part of their academic career in the country of origin).

We also ask about the effect of repeated collaboration with mobile scientists. A single collaboration with a mobile scientist might introduce a non-mobile to a foreign collaborator. We ask whether that event has a long-lasting effect or whether sustained interaction with foreigners must be supported by repeated interactions with mobile scientists. To identify a causal impact of mobile scientists on the foreign collaborations of non-mobile scientists, we conduct an event study.

Our work studies scientists from Colombia and Brazil. In recent decades, both the Brazilian and Colombian governments have established standardized scientific curriculum vitae (CV) platforms to track the careers of their scientists. These platforms are unique scientific databases with information on a scientist’s trajectory, including academic and biographical background and publications. We rely on this database to identify mobile and non-mobile scientists using their academic formation and work locations after the Ph.D. Because some scientists might not update their CVs after they move abroad, we combine the CV data with scholarship data. We merge bibliometric data from OpenAlex to complete the information on the scientists’ publications, all their co-authors, and complete their mobility information through affiliations. Our findings show that interacting with a mobile scientist positively correlates with more publications co-authored with foreign scientists. The share of publications co-authored with foreign scientists also increases, indicating that non-mobile scientists shift their research portfolio towards international collaborations. Results also hold when we control for the non-mobile scientist’s visibility (publications and citations) and past stock of collaborations with foreign scientists. Increasing the number of unique mobile scientists with whom they co-publish, is associated with increasing collaborations with foreign scientists.

Not all mobile scientists are made equal. Their relevance to increasing the international collaborations of non-mobile colleagues is inversely proportional to the average time they spend in their home countries, roughly speaking. That is, publishing with returnees is not associated with increasing collaborations with foreign scientists once we control for the non-mobile scientist's visibility and past foreign collaborations. The elasticity between the number of collaborations with mobiles and foreigners is larger for the diaspora than for intermittent, particularly in the Colombian case.

We also find that not all non-mobile scientists benefit equally. STEM non-mobile scientists benefit less from co-authoring with mobile scientists than scientists in the social sciences and humanities in Colombia, probably because STEM scientists have a higher propensity of being included in international teams by the nature of their work, e.g. to run experiments in local contexts, regardless of their interactions with mobile colleagues. Another explanation is that STEM scientists may need more infrastructure to conduct research, which is available in Brazil, but not in Colombia: co-authoring with mobile scientists may bring networks, but not labs. However, STEM non-mobile scientists benefit from diaspora scientists as much as non-mobile scientists in SSH even in Colombia.

The Difference-in-Difference event study results confirm that non-mobile scientists who co-author with a mobile scientist publish more with foreign colleagues than their Brazilian or Colombian peers who do not co-author with mobile scientists. The more mobile scientists they co-author with, the greater the extent to which their work includes foreign scientists over the years. Before co-authoring with a mobile, there is no significant difference between non-mobile scientists in relation to the number of publications co-authored with foreign scientists. The year in which they co-author with mobile scientists, though, the number of publications with foreign scientist increases by 20% with respect to their non-mobile colleagues. However, this positive effect is due to the non-mobile scientist joining a team including both mobile and foreign scientists. In both countries, the benefit of a single collaboration with a mobile scientist quickly goes to zero. The non-mobile scientist who collaborates with only one or two unique mobile scientists experience this benefit only for the year of the collaboration. With three or more such collaborations, the effect is longer-lived, but it is sustained by continuous interactions with mobile scientists. To sustain a higher publication rate with foreign scientists, the non-mobile scientists must continue collaborating with mobile scientists. In other words, mobile scientists connect the non-mobile to foreign scientists but retain the role of obligatory gateways for further connections.

Results from the event study are similar for STEM and SSH. One interesting difference is that in Colombia SSH non-mobile scientists need to collaborate with more mobile scientists to maintain their connections to foreign scientists than in STEM. DiD results confirm that mobile scientists that return to their home countries (returnees) and those that stay abroad for a while (intermittent) or forever (diaspora) have a different effect. The impact of returnees in connecting non-mobile scientists with foreign scientists lasts only the year of the collaboration with the first returnee. In contrast, of intermittent and diaspora lasts for the five years that follow. Again, this effect is significant only when the non-mobile collaborates maintain active collaborations with several diaspora or intermittent scientists that act as gatekeepers.

Our analysis of two countries in terms of size, scientific and education systems, geography, and history shows remarkably similar results. This lends further credibility to our results and their generalizability to other middle-income countries, which can use them to think about their education and research policies concerning mobility.

Literature review

International scientific mobility

The idea that international scientific mobility affects countries' scientific performance has been in the literature for several years. Many of these studies build on ideas implicit in the concept of Scientific and Technical Human Capital model (STCH) (Bozeman et al., 2001). First, an experience abroad will likely increase a scientist's human capital (e.g., knowledge, skills, and abilities) by allowing the scientist to tap into novel knowledge, absorb tacit knowledge, and access infrastructure. Second, an experience abroad may enlarge personal and professional networks. This implies that international mobility should be positively associated with a scientist having higher research capacity and social capital (see Edler, Fier, & Grimpe, 2011; Jonkers & Cruz-Castro, 2013; Liang, Gu, & Nyland, 2022). Starting with the idea that mobility may increase a scientist's Scientific and Technical Human Capital, studies primarily focus on demonstrating the positive impact of mobility on a scientist's performance and network.

A first group of studies investigates the scientific performance of mobile scientists, concluding that mobile scientists have higher performance than scientists without foreign experience (non-mobile scientists) across different scientific fields and countries. For example, relying on bibliometric data, Jonkers & Cruz-Castro (2013) looking at 124 life-science Argentinean scientists find that mobile scientists have more international co-publications than non-mobile scientists. Relatedly, Aykac (2021) documents that Turkish mobile scientists with research stays in the United States obtain more citations than non-mobile scientists without foreign experience. Combining bibliometric and survey data on 47,000 scientists from 16 countries, Franzoni, Scellato, & Stephan (2014) find that international mobility increases the number of articles they publish in high-impact journals.

The second group of studies investigates scientists' social capital by testing whether mobile scientists have more extensive co-authorship networks – a proxy for professional networks – than non-mobile scientists (Gibson & McKenzie, 2014; Jonkers & Tijssen, 2008; Petersen, 2018; Scellato, Franzoni, & Stephan, 2015). A recurring finding is that mobile scientists display more co-authors than non-mobile scientists (Gibson & McKenzie, 2014; Petersen, 2018). But studies also tend to agree that collaboration with host country scientists falls when mobile scientists return to their home countries (Jonkers & Tijssen, 2008; Kahn & MacGarvie, 2012). Nonetheless, despite the reduction of international collaboration when they return home, mobile scientists collaborate more with foreign scientists and have larger foreign capital than home country's non-mobile scientists (Wang, Hooi, Li, & Chou, 2019).

A third group of studies compares the performance of diaspora, returnees, and non-mobile scientists (Cao et al., 2020; Scellato et al., 2015; Velema, 2012). Several studies report that diaspora scientists have a higher performance (e.g., publish more articles and receive more citations) and have more extensive networks (number of foreign co-authors) than the other two types of scientists (Aykac, 2021). Generally, diaspora scientists tend to have a certain level of expertise and networks, allowing them to remain at highly competitive institutions abroad. Second, these scientists usually work in environments with high-quality infrastructures, leading researchers, and more funding opportunities (Liang et al., 2022; Velema, 2012). Hence, they access resources that are scarcer in their home countries, enabling them to research at the scientific frontier. Studies also recount that non-mobile scientists cite returnees more frequently and co-author more with returnees than with diaspora scientists. Geographical proximity and returnees' willingness to align the research agenda to topics investigated in their home countries explain this latter finding (Kahn & MacGarvie, 2012, 2016; Tripl, 2013).

Cooperation in science

It is commonplace now that science is a cooperative endeavor. Between 2000 and 2009 the proportion of papers in the Web of Science with multiple authors rose from 69 to 78% (Gazni, Sugimoto, & Didegah, 2012). Similarly, the number of authors per paper rose from 3.3 to 4.1 on average. Driving this may be the importance of interpersonal ties for knowledge flows (for example, Singh, 2005) and increased specialization. Thus, making links with collaborators becomes part of the scientific process. Trust (cohesiveness), similarity (homophily), and structural position have all been found to explain tie formation in general (Abbasi, 2016), and these factors have been found to be present in tie formation among scientists (Dahlander & McFarland, 2013; Rivera León, Cowan, & Müller, 2016).

However, less studied than link formation in general is how a scientist's (non-network) properties might affect either link formation or the performance of nearby (in network space) scientists. One such example investigating the structural position of star medical scientists in a co-authorship network, finds that scientists who provide more access to unique nodes have a more significant impact on the scientific output of their peers (Mohnen, 2022). Another study that investigates the peer effect of Chinese returnee scientists finds that returnees do not increase their peers' international collaborations (Yang, Cai, & Li, 2022). Contrarily, Barnard, Cowan, & Müller (forthcoming) find different results. Investigating whether there is a social capital spillover among South African scientists, the authors find that scientists with cumulated foreign social capital help other scientists to form foreign ties. This paper is closest in spirit to the current paper in that both ask whether a mobile scientist's foreign social (scientific) capital facilitates certain types of link formation of non-mobile colleagues.

Mobility, cooperation and tie formation

Different studies suggest that mobile scientists connect the science systems in their home countries and those they have sojourned (Gibson & McKenzie, 2014; Jöns, 2009). Based on the premise that mobile scientists have more significant foreign social capital, these studies argue that mobile scientists, especially returnees, serve as bridges between the local and global scientific systems. To a great extent, though, these studies focus on “first order effects”. They compare the properties of various types of mobile scientists with non-mobile scientists. Trippel (2013), for example, shows that mobile star scientists retain links of different kinds (including co-authorship) with home scientists (who themselves might or might not be mobile). Gibson & McKenzie (2014) find that in three small Pacific Island countries mobile scientists (diaspora or returnees) have more international co-authors than non-mobile scientists. Scellato et al. (2015) show that, in general, migrants have more internationally focused collaboration networks than non-mobile scientists.

These studies all show that mobile scientists may serve to connect the home science system to the wider world of science. And they can do it in various ways. What is not explicitly addressed in these studies, however, is whether mobile scientists assist non-mobile scientists in forming international connections. Does a mobile scientist provide a conduit through which a non-mobile scientist can interact directly (more specifically, become co-authors) with scientists in the rest of the world?

Institutional context

Exploring mobile scientists' role in linking non-mobile and foreign scientists, we examine Brazil and Colombia. Brazil, Latin America's largest scientific system, boasts 4,560 graduate programs, top research institutes, and federal and regional funding agencies, ranking 13th globally with 3.2% of world's scientific publications (Academia Brasileira de Ciências, 2021; Negri, 2018). Colombia ranks 5th in Latin America, recently improving its scientific system,

increasing graduate programs, and establishing a ministry for science, technology, and innovation (Observatorio Colombiano de Ciencia y Tecnología, 2021).

Despite progress, both countries lag behind high-income nations in knowledge output. To enhance scientific productivity, they invest in citizens' Ph.D. training abroad. Brazil's Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), National Council for Scientific and Technological Development CNPq, and Colombia's Administrative Department of Science, Technology, and Innovation (Colciencias) and the Foundation for the Future of Colombia (Colfuturo) support international doctoral training. For example, in Colombia, with 3,425 sponsored individuals since 1992, the annual grantee numbers have risen from 20 before 2006 to 208 until 2021.

Considering Brazil and Colombia's significant investment in international Ph.D. mobility programs, we study their impact, focusing on potential externalities in connecting domestic and foreign scientists.

Data and empirical strategy

Data sources

We combined data on Curriculum Vitae (CVs), PhD scholarships, and bibliometric data of a large sample of scientists in Colombia and Brazil.

Colombian and Brazilian governments have established public CV platforms to track national researchers' progress and standardize recruitment in research and teaching positions. In Brazil, CNPq has developed the Lattes platform, and in Colombia the Colombian Ministry of Science has developed the CVLAC platform. Brazil and Colombia's governments, universities, and scientific institutions use Lattes and CVLAC to recruit scientists, allocate grants and scholarships, and decide on promotions.

Lattes and CVLAC are unique datasets with detailed, self-reported information on scientists' academic backgrounds, publications, and careers. We use these sources to extract information on: nationality, academic background and publications. We extracted these data from Lattes and CVLAC by accessing available governmental open data repositories. In the case of Brazil we used Mena-Chalco and Junior's dataset (2009).

Because not all mobile scientists have the incentive to update their CVs on Lattes and CVLAC when moving abroad to study, we retrieved data on scholarship holders from the main Brazilian and Colombian funding agencies to improve the data on mobile scientists' web pages. For Brazil, we obtained data from CNPq and Capes. For Colombia, we obtained data from the official lists published by the Ministry of Science, the Colfuturo Foundation, and Fulbright Colombia. We extracted information on the names of the scholarship holders, their PhD starting date, disciplines, and the countries to which they applied.

To build the mobility pattern and co-authorship network of Brazilian and Colombian scientists, we retrieved bibliometric data from OpenAlex, a global open-access database with more than 200 million scientific publications, which builds on Microsoft Academic Graph and is regularly updated using several sources (Singh Chawla, 2022). We use the bibliometric data to determine the publication records of the Brazilian and Colombian scientists retrieved from Lattes and CVLAC and compute: 1) their mobility patterns based on country of affiliation; 2) their co-

authorship networks (including with foreign scientists); 3) academic seniority, and 4) scientific productivity.

Data matching

To build our database, for each scientist in Lattes and CVLAC we match information from the scholarship and bibliometric data. First, we matched the scholarship lists to Lattes and CVLAC using fuzzy matching of names, disciplines, and institutions. We manually checked the results. Second, we matched all scientists in Lattes and CVLAC with their publications in OpenAlex using disambiguation procedures developed in the scientometrics literature (D'Angelo & van Eck, 2020). We combined the following information: author names fuzzy match, ORCID identifiers, publications title, other bibliographic metadata (e.g. ISSN, DOI, year, volume), DOI, and self-citations. We defined several selection criteria based on the above data to maximize precision and recall.

The initial number of scientists in Brazil (Lattes) is 139,655, and in Colombia (CVLAC) is 28,729. We matched with high precision a large sample of 102,422 (73%) scientists in Brazil and 19,661 (68%) in Colombia.

Definition of mobility patterns and foreign collaborations

In our analysis, we distinguish between three main groups of scientists: mobile, non-mobile, and foreigner. Following the literature, we define mobile scientists as those who have moved abroad to obtain their full doctoral training (Brazil and Colombia) or moved abroad after their PhD (Brazil) (Kahn & MacGarvie, 2012; Liang et al., 2022).

We define non-mobile scientists as those who have done graduate training in Brazil or Colombia and never moved to a foreign country for more than 11 months to work in academia. We focus on researchers registered in Lattes and CVLAV with a Ph.D. in progress, completed, or listed as grantees of scholarships to study abroad. Because in Colombia, it is possible to access academic careers without holding a Ph.D. degree, we extended our definition of non-mobile scientists to those without a PhD but with at least 3 publications.

We further divide mobile scientists into three types that may have different patterns of interaction with non-mobile scientists and different connectivity to foreign scientists: returnees (R), diaspora (D), and intermittent (I). Returnees are scientists who have returned home indefinitely no more than one year after their Ph.D. and never spent more than one year abroad over the rest of their career until the last year of observation (no foreign affiliations among their publications since their Ph.D.). Diaspora are scientists who never returned home to work in academia after finishing their Ph.D. abroad (no Colombian/Brazilian affiliation among their publications). Intermittent are scientists who returned home to work for at least one year and worked abroad for at least one year (this includes Brazilian scientists who obtained a Ph.D. in Brazil and moved after).

We followed Barnard et al. (forthcoming) to identify foreign collaborators of the non-mobile Colombian and Brazilian scientists. We identified as foreigners all co-authors not present in Lattes and CVLAC. Because scientists may migrate before their Ph.D., or obtain a foreign scholarship, some of the scientists not registered in Lattes or CVLAC may be Colombian or Brazilian. Identifying them as foreigners would overestimate collaborations with foreign scientists and underestimate collaborations with mobile scientists. To avoid this bias, we isolate Colombian and Brazilian mobile scientists in OpenAlex who do not appear in Lattes and CVLAC in three steps. First, we created a list of common Brazilian or Colombian name-

surname combinations from the most frequent combinations in CVLAC and Lattes databases and national registries of names in Colombia and Brazil. Second, we matched common name-surname combinations with the foreign coauthors identified in OpenAlex. Third, we redefined as mobile-matched authors who have published only in national journals or were affiliated only with national organizations throughout their careers, based on OpenAlex. All other co-authors were defined as foreigners.

Empirical strategy

Ordinary least square strategy

Our objective is to study whether the collaboration between non-mobile scientists and foreign scientists is influenced by collaboration with mobile scientists. In other words, does collaborating with mobile scientists connect the non-mobile with foreign scientists and thus increase the chances of further collaboration with them? We identify collaboration as a co-authorship. First, we investigate the intensive margin of collaborating with a mobile scientist by estimating the probability that a home scientist collaborates with any number of foreign scientists as a function of collaborating with a mobile scientist. Second, we investigate the extensive margin: we estimate the number of collaborations of non-mobile scientists with foreign scientists as a function of collaborating with mobile scientists. Third, we explore how results differ for different groups of scientists. We explore field heterogeneity, and ask whether non-mobile scientists in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) gain from collaborations with mobile scientists relative to scientists in social sciences and humanities (SSH). We also distinguish between different types of mobile scientists (returnees, intermittent and diaspora).

We estimate two main equations, separately for Brazil and Colombia.

Intensive Margin. We use Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and estimate the following linear probability model (LPM):

$$y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i,t} + \beta_2 STEM_i + \beta_3 STEM_i * X_{i,t} + \Gamma \mathcal{E}_{i,t-1} + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

where y_{it} is a binary variable indicating whether a non-mobile scientist collaborates at least once with a foreign scientist (at least one co-authored publication); $X_{i,t}$ is our main variable of interest, which measures the collaborations of non-mobile with mobile scientists using two different specifications: a dummy variable equal to one if the non-mobile scientist has collaborated with at least one mobile scientist ($AMM_{i,t}$), or the cumulative sum of unique mobile scientists with whom they have collaborated ($StkMobSciEncou_{i,t}$); $STEM_i$ is a dummy equal to one for non-mobile scientists in the STEM fields; $\mathcal{E}_{i,t-1}$ is a set of control variables: ($AvPub_{i,t-1}$) is the logarithm of the lagged value of average annual publications of the non-mobile scientist over the years since first publication, to control for productivity; ($AvCit_{i,t-1}$) measures the logarithm of the lagged average of citations over the years since first publication to control for scientist i 's visibility; ($StkFRGN_{i,t-1}$) is the logarithm of the non-mobile scientist i 's past stock of foreign co-authors; ($YrSinFP_{i,t}$) years of experience measured as the number of years since the first publication; ($Gender_i$) takes the value of one for male non-mobile scientists. In this first specification, all observations are pooled in one single period, such that a home scientist that appears more than one year is considered a different person.

Extensive margin

To estimate the extensive margin, we use a panel model with fixed effects as defined in Equation 2:

$$y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i,t} + \beta_2 STEM_i + \beta_3 STEM_i * X_{i,t} + \Gamma \mathcal{E}_{i,t-1} + \varphi_i + \psi_i + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

where y_{it} can be one of the following outputs: 1) share of publications with foreign co-authors; 2) the share of foreign co-authors; 3) the logarithm of the number of publications with foreign co-authors; 4) the logarithm of number of foreign co-authors; $STEM_i$ is a dummy equal to one for non-mobile scientists in the STEM fields; $\mathcal{E}_{i,t-1}$ is the set of control variables described above; $\varphi_i + \psi_i$ are, respectively, discipline and non-mobile scientist fixed effects.

Difference in differences event study

We rely on a difference-in-difference event study design to identify the causal effect of co-authoring with mobile scientists on the number of co-authored publications of non-mobile with foreign scientists (Borusyak, Hull, & Jaravel, 2022). We use the difference-in-differences estimator with treatment over multiple periods developed by Callaway & Sant'Anna (2021) to estimate the average treatment effect for non-mobile scientists treated in different years. This setup follows a staggered treatment: once treated, a non-mobile scientist remains treated for the following years. In our study, the treatment group is formed by Brazilian and Colombian non-mobile scientists who have co-authored with mobile scientists at least once during the period we observe them. The control group is formed by all other non-mobile Brazilian and Colombian scientists who have never co-authored with a mobile scientist. The estimated outcome indicates the intensity of co-authoring with foreign scientists. To simplify, we use the number of publications co-authored with foreign scientists.

Formally, our difference-in-differences specification is then expressed as:

$$Y_{i,t} = \alpha_1^{g,t} + \alpha_2^{g,t} G_g + \alpha_3^{g,t} 1\{T = t\} + \beta (G_g \cdot 1\{T = t\}) + x_i' \theta + \epsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

where $Y_{i,t}$ is the (log-transformed) number of publications co-authored with foreign scientists by the non-mobile scientist i in year t ; G_g is a binary variable that equals one if a non-mobile scientist belongs to the treatment group and becomes first treated in year g and equals zero for the control group; $\alpha_2^{g,t}$ is the coefficient for the treatment group dummy; β represents the average treatment effect; $\alpha_3^{g,t}$ represents the coefficient for the post treatment dummy; x_i' represents a vector of control variables that are not influenced by the treatment: tenure (years since first publication) and gender. We have checked that there is no statistically significant difference for observable features that can be endogenous but can also be influenced by the treatment (publications and citations) before the treatment between treated and non-treated non-mobile scientists. Following Callaway & Sant'Anna (2021) recommendations and Abadie, Athey, Imbens, & Wooldridge's (2022), we clustered standard errors at the individual level.

Throughout their career, non-mobile scientists may co-author with more than one mobile scientist in one or more years. This means that some of the non-mobile scientists are treated more than once. To distinguish the effect of one versus multiple treatments, we split the sample according to the number of unique mobile scientists with whom a non-mobile scientist has co-authored. We consider the treatment to be the year of the first co-authored publication because our research question is about the effect of the interaction with a mobile, which does not exclude that the interaction can last for more than one period. Future research may distinguish different

types of more or less stable collaborations. We thus estimate the impact of the first co-authorship with a mobile scientist on the number of co-authored publications with foreign authors for the following samples: 1) non-mobile scientists that have co-authored with any number of mobile scientists (all collaborations); 2) non-mobile scientists that have co-authored with one unique mobile co-author; 3) with two unique mobile co-authors; and 4) with three unique mobile co-authors. We analyze the Colombian and the Brazilian samples separately.

Results

Ordinary least square results: Probability of collaborating with at least one foreign co-author
Tables 1A and B report results from Equation 1, estimating the probability that a non-mobile scientist co-authors with at least one foreign scientist if they have co-authored with any number of mobile scientists. In columns 1 to 4 the key independent variable is a dummy taking the value 1 if the non-mobile scientist has had at least one co-authorship with a mobile scientist. Columns 5 to 8 by contrast the total number of unique mobile scientists with whom the non-mobile scientist has co-authored.

The tables show that collaborating at least once with a mobile scientist (column 1) is related to a 19 percentage points higher probability of collaborating with a foreign scientist in Colombia and 27 percentage points in Brazil. In both cases, this value falls to 11 percentage points when we add the controls (columns 2, 3, and 4). Nonetheless, the results remain highly significant at 0.01% in both countries. This implies that, once we control for observable features that influence the probability of foreign co-authorship (including previous experience of co-authoring with them), scientists who have spent their entire careers at home are 11% more likely to co-author (again) with a foreign scientist after having co-authored with at least one mobile scientist.

As the number of collaborations with mobile scientists increases, the probability of collaborating with a foreign scientist also increases (cols 5-8). In Colombia (Table 1A), column 6 shows that a 10% increase in the stock of mobile scientists with whom the non-mobile collaborates is related to an increase of eight percentage points in the probability of having a foreign co-author. Similarly, in the Brazilian case (Table 1B), a 10% increase is associated with an increase of five percentage points in the probability of having a foreign co-author.

The drop in the coefficient when adding controls shows that past performance of a non-mobile scientist is correlated with collaborating with both mobile and foreign scientists. The estimates for the coefficients of the controls are intuitively appealing and in concord with results in the literature. In columns 2 and 6, we find that an increase of 10% in the average number of past publications is related to an 11 percentage point positive change in the probability of having a foreign co-author for Colombian scientists and to around 16 percent points change for Brazilian scientists. In cols 3, 4, 7, and 8, we find that scientists' visibility measured by the average number of past citations is statistically and positively correlated with co-authoring with a foreign scientist. Finally, having co-authored in the past with foreign scientists is also related to a higher likelihood of co-authoring with foreign scientists in the future (variable `Log_StkFRGN_lag`).

Gender and seniority also correlate to the probability of having foreign collaboration. We observe a gender bias: a male non-mobile scientist is more likely to have a foreign co-author than is a female, after controlling for all other observable characteristics. Additionally, we find

that seniority is negatively correlated with the likelihood that non-mobile scientists co-author with foreign scientists, especially in Colombia (although the coefficient is rather small).

Results suggest a difference between STEM and SSH subjects (columns 4 and 8), following different patterns in Colombia and Brazil. First, Colombian non-mobile STEM scientists are two to four percentage points more likely to have at least a foreign co-author, whereas in Brazil they are two to three percentage points more likely to have at least a foreign co-author. Second, in both Colombia and Brazil in STEM the gain from collaboration with more mobiles is slightly smaller than it is in SSH. The probability of co-authoring with a foreign scientist for a 100% increase in mobile co-authors decreases from 11% to 7% in Colombia and from 8% to 7% in Brazil (col 8). Finally, we do not find significant disciplinary differences (between STEM and SSH) on the probability that a non-mobile scientist collaborates with at least one foreign scientist.

Table 1A. Foreign collaboration (Colombia)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	<i>FRGN Collab</i>	<i>FRGN Collab</i>	<i>FRGN Collab</i>	<i>FRGN Collab</i>	<i>FRGN Collab</i>	<i>FRGN Collab</i>	<i>FRGN Collab</i>	<i>FRGN Collab</i>
AfterMeetin gMobile	0.186*** (0.00340)	0.110*** (0.00368)	0.116*** (0.00362)	0.118*** (0.00519)				
Log_StkMob SciEncou					0.163*** (0.00259)	0.0838*** (0.00289)	0.0699*** (0.00281)	0.105*** (0.00401)
Log_AvPub_ lag		0.116*** (0.00439)				0.117*** (0.00438)		
Log_StkFRG N_lag		0.110*** (0.00167)	0.0970*** (0.00189)	0.0966*** (0.00190)		0.106*** (0.00168)	0.0611*** (0.00188)	0.0923*** (0.00190)
YrsSinceFirs tPub		0.000736 (0.000385)	-0.00323*** (0.000366)	-0.00316*** (0.000367)		0.000552 (0.000388)	-0.00351*** (0.000362)	-0.00332*** (0.000370)
Gender (Male: 1)		0.0175*** (0.00335)	0.0206*** (0.00335)	0.0201*** (0.00335)		0.0169*** (0.00335)	0.0190*** (0.00329)	0.0192*** (0.00335)
Log_AvCits_ lag			0.0700*** (0.00257)	0.0694*** (0.00258)			0.136*** (0.00242)	0.0701*** (0.00258)
STEM				0.0151** (0.00484)				0.0365*** (0.00476)
STEM*c.Lo g_StkMobSc iEncou								-0.0300*** (0.00504)
STEM* AfterMeetin gMobile				-0.00439 (0.00667)				
cons	0.229*** (0.00238)	-0.00322 (0.00663)	0.0789*** (0.00608)	0.0718*** (0.00652)	0.215*** (0.00238)	0.00403 (0.00663)	0.0904*** (0.00594)	0.0698*** (0.00649)
N	72548	66683	66683	66683	72548	66683	66683	66683
R ²	0.040	0.166	0.167	0.167	0.052	0.165	0.195	0.167

$p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Table 1B. Foreign collaboration (Brazil)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	FRGN Collab	FRGN Collab	FRGN Collab	FRGN Collab	FRGN Collab	FRGN Collab	FRGN Collab	FRGN Collab
AfterMeetingMobile	0.266*** (0.000985)	0.0993*** (0.00115)	0.118*** (0.00117)	0.109*** (0.00191)				
Log_StkMobScientistEncou					0.142*** (0.000424)	0.0527*** (0.000612)	0.0737*** (0.000684)	0.0826*** (0.00116)
Log_AvPub_lag		0.184*** (0.00137)				0.166*** (0.00145)		
Log_StkFRGN_lag		0.0769*** (0.000587)	0.108*** (0.000541)	0.108*** (0.000541)		0.0733*** (0.000594)	0.104*** (0.000549)	0.103*** (0.000550)
YrsSinceFirstPub		0.00220*** (0.000104)	-0.00294*** (0.000102)	-0.00306*** (0.000103)		0.00136*** (0.000107)	-0.00292*** (0.000102)	-0.00312*** (0.000102)
Gender (Male:1)		0.0143*** (0.000962)	0.0174*** (0.000970)	0.0181*** (0.000971)		0.0144*** (0.000962)	0.0169*** (0.000969)	0.0177*** (0.000970)
Log_AvCits_lag			0.0361*** (0.000683)	0.0370*** (0.000699)			0.00912*** (0.000790)	0.0111*** (0.000802)
STEM				-0.0216*** (0.00135)				-0.0163*** (0.00133)
STEM*AfterMeetingMobile				0.0163*** (0.00220)				
STEM*log_stkMobScientistEncou								-0.00797*** (0.00119)
constant	0.218*** (0.000687)	0.0181*** (0.00111)	0.118*** (0.000939)	0.130*** (0.00121)	0.203*** (0.000669)	0.0412*** (0.00114)	0.127*** (0.000929)	0.136*** (0.00122)
N	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551
R ²	0.074	0.168	0.153	0.153	0.108	0.168	0.155	0.156

$p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Share of publications with foreign co-authors (over total publications)

Tables 2A and B display results for the yearly average share of publications with foreign co-authors (over total publications of a non-mobile scientist), including scientific field (cols. 1 and 4) or individual fixed effects (cols 3 and 6) to control for unobserved characteristics that vary across disciplines or scientists. We report the results for both independent variable specifications: co-authoring with any number of mobile scientists (columns 1-3), and the number of mobile scientists with whom the non-mobile co-authors (columns 4-6).

After controlling for the non-mobile visibility and stock of foreign co-authors, interacting with a mobile scientist is positively associated with the share of publications with foreign co-authors. The magnitude of the main independent variable coefficient in col 1 with field fixed effects suggests that meeting a mobile is associated with an increase in the share of publications with foreign co-authors by 3.7 for Colombian scientists and 3.9 for Brazilian scientists. In the case of Colombia, the coefficient increases for the individual scientist (when we include individual fixed effects): after a scientist co-authors with a mobile scientist, they increase their share of publications with foreign co-authors by 5.8. This suggests that in the Colombian case collaborations with a mobile scientist are more relevant to explain an increase in collaborations with foreign authors before and after the collaboration for the same scientist, than when comparing non-mobile scientists that collaborate with mobile scientists and those who do not. This is not the case in Brazil though: when controlling for individual fixed-effects the coefficient is smaller. Non observable difference among scientists explain part of the different propensity to co-authors with foreign scientists, when measured with the share of publications.

When we use a count of collaborations (columns 4-6) rather than a binary indicator, results differ for Colombia and Brazil. Individual fixed has again a large effect on coefficient estimates in Colombia, and improves the predictive power (at least as measured by R2) of the regression: the coefficient estimates (column 6) indicate that the elasticity of increasing the number of mobile collaborators on the share of publications co-authored with a foreign scientist among non-mobile scientists is about 6 percent. In Brazil, instead, the number of collaborations with mobile scientists has a small coefficient, significant only at 10% when we control for non-observed differences among the non-mobile scientists.

Disciplinary effects are difficult to identify. When individual fixed effects are included, discipline has no effect on foreign collaboration patterns. This might not be surprising as discipline are largely captured in individual fixed effects (few change from STEM to SSH over their careers). However, when discipline is treated specifically (excluding individual effects) we see first that Colombian STEM researchers are more international than are SSH researchers (column 5). At the same time, though, in Colombia but not in Brazil, discipline interacts with the main effect of interest. On average, the elasticity of an increase the number of mobile interactions is about 0.03. However, the interaction between STEM discipline and number of interactions is about -0.026. This suggests that the net effect of increasing interactions with mobile scientists for a Colombian STEM researcher is close to zero.

Table 2A. Average share of foreign publication, panel (Colombia)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	<i>AvShare FRGNpub</i>	<i>AvShare FRGNpub</i>	<i>AvShare FRGNpub</i>	<i>AvShare FRGNpub</i>	<i>AvShare FRGNpub</i>	<i>AvShare FRGNpub</i>
AfterMeetingMobile	0.0366*** (0.00218)	0.0420*** (0.00309)	0.0580*** (0.00399)			
Log_StkMobSciEncou				0.0135*** (0.00172)	0.0300*** (0.00239)	0.0565*** (0.00337)
Log_StkFRGN_lag	0.119*** (0.00114)	0.118*** (0.00113)	0.0850*** (0.00185)	0.118*** (0.00114)	0.117*** (0.00113)	0.0832*** (0.00187)
YrsSinceFirstPub	-0.00672*** (0.000219)	-0.00672*** (0.000218)	0.00473*** (0.000288)	-0.00630*** (0.000220)	-0.00628*** (0.000220)	0.00479*** (0.000292)
Gender (Male: 1)	0.0118*** (0.00204)	0.0105*** (0.00199)	0 (.)	0.0116*** (0.00204)	0.0102*** (0.00199)	0 (.)
Log_AvCits_lag	0.0352*** (0.00153)	0.0355*** (0.00153)	-0.0363*** (0.00231)	0.0375*** (0.00154)	0.0382*** (0.00154)	-0.0409*** (0.00233)
STEM		0.0191*** (0.00288)	0 (.)		0.0344*** (0.00284)	0 (.)
STEM*AfterMeetingMo bile		-0.00736 (0.00397)	0.00622 (0.00482)			
STEM*Log_StkMob SciEncou					-0.0263*** (0.00300)	-0.00944* (0.00393)
cons	0.0944*** (0.00368)	0.0862*** (0.00388)	0.0982*** (0.00183)	0.113*** (0.00214)	0.0947*** (0.00257)	0.101*** (0.00181)
Field FE	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No
Individual FE	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
N	66683	66683	66637	66683	66683	66637
R ²	0.297	0.296	0.562	0.295	0.294	0.562

$p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Table 2B. Average share of foreign publication, panel (Brazil)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	<i>AvgshareFRGNpub</i>	<i>AvgshareFRGNpub</i>	<i>AvgshareFRGNpub</i>	<i>AvgshareFRGNpub</i>	<i>AvgshareFRGNpub</i>	<i>AvgshareFRGNpub</i>
AAfterMeetingMobile	0.0392*** (0.00512)	0.0228** (0.00635)	0.0265*** (0.00511)			
Log_StkMobScientistEncou				0.0135*** (0.00259)	0.00820 (0.00538)	0.0189* (0.00681)
Log_stockFRGN_lag	0.0978*** (0.00225)	0.0986*** (0.00228)	0.0513*** (0.00210)	0.0981*** (0.00230)	0.0988*** (0.00234)	0.0507*** (0.00197)
YearsSinceFirstPub	-0.00583*** (0.000313)	-0.00577*** (0.000313)	0.00332*** (0.000388)	-0.00566*** (0.000325)	-0.00560*** (0.000325)	0.00359*** (0.000424)
Gender (Male: 1)	0.00537 (0.00267)	0.00849** (0.00223)		0.00504 (0.00258)	0.00822** (0.00224)	
Log_AVG_citations_lag	-0.0145*** (0.00124)	-0.0167*** (0.00119)	-0.0394*** (0.00169)	-0.0167*** (0.00186)	-0.0183*** (0.00150)	-0.0500*** (0.00228)
STEM		0.00275 (0.00419)			0.0103* (0.00418)	
STEM*AfterMeetingMobile		0.0241** (0.00672)	0.0254*** (0.00562)			
STEM*Log_stkMobScientistEncou					0.00640 (0.00520)	0.00754 (0.00625)
constant	0.124*** (0.00233)	0.119*** (0.00362)	0.135*** (0.00190)	0.130*** (0.00221)	0.121*** (0.00387)	0.139*** (0.00178)
Field FE	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No
Individual FE	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
<i>N</i>	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551
<i>R</i> ²	0.195	0.195	0.405	0.193	0.192	0.404

$p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Number of publications with foreign co-authors

The share of publications with foreign co-authors (Tables 2A and B) is affected by overall productivity of the non-mobile scientist. Interaction with a mobile scientist may have two effects: it may change publications overall and the extent of “internationality” of a scientist’s co-authors (publications with foreign scientists). Thus an increase in the proportion of “foreign” papers may be driven by a reduction in the number of “domestic” papers, rather than an increase in publications with foreign authors. To address this, we report results for the number of publications with foreign co-authors in Tables 3A (Colombia) and 3B (Brazil) (for at least one collaboration with mobile scientists in columns (1-3), and for the stock of collaborations with mobile scientists in columns (4-6)).

Results are overall similar to those discussed in the previous subsection, suggesting that the higher share of publications with foreign co-authors following collaboration with mobile scientists is driven by an increase in the number of publications with foreign co-authors rather than a decrease in purely domestic publications. Collaborating with a mobile scientist is associated with an increase by 5% (7%) in the number of publications with foreign co-authors (column 2 in a log-log specification) for Colombian (Brazilian) non-mobile scientists. When we control for individual fixed effects, the magnitude of the coefficient is similar: 7% (column 3). This finding corroborates the previous results: meeting a mobile may be important for a home scientist to forge in a strategy of accessing foreign collaborators.

The coefficients on the log stock of unique mobile scientists’ collaborations in the last three columns (4-6) show that an increase in mobile scientists’ collaborators is positively related to an increase in average publications with foreign scientists. For example, in col 6 (with individual fixed effects), the elasticity of foreign publication concerning number of unique mobile scientists with whom non-mobile collaborate is 0.1 (0.12) for Colombia (Brazil). So a doubling in the stock of mobile collaborators in a non-mobile scientist’s career leads to a 10% increase in the number of publications with foreign co-authors in the case of Colombia and 12% in the case of Brazil. Comparing Tables 3B and 2B shows that the small coefficients in Table

2B are due to Brazilian scientists increasing publication with and without foreign collaborators at the same rate when they co-author with mobile scientists: the number of foreign collaborations increase, but not the share.

Table 3A. Average foreign publication, panel (Colombia)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	<i>Log_</i> <i>AvFRGpub</i>	<i>Log_</i> <i>AvFRGpub</i>	<i>Log_</i> <i>AvFRGpub</i>	<i>Log_</i> <i>AvFRGpub</i>	<i>Log_</i> <i>AvFRGpub</i>	<i>Log_</i> <i>AvFRGpub</i>
AfterMeetingMobile	0.0506***	0.0515***	0.0743***			
	(0.00329)	(0.00325)	(0.00596)			
Log				0.0440***	0.0554***	0.104***
StkMobSci Encou				(0.00259)	(0.00360)	(0.00502)
Log_StkFRGN_lag	0.175***	0.174***	0.127***	0.173***	0.171***	0.120***
	(0.00171)	(0.00170)	(0.00276)	(0.00172)	(0.00171)	(0.00278)
YrsSinceFirstPub	-0.0111***	-0.0113***	0.00357***	-0.0114***	-0.0115***	0.00174***
	(0.000330)	(0.000329)	(0.000430)	(0.000332)	(0.000332)	(0.000434)
Gender	0.0302***	0.0313***	0	0.0299***	0.0307***	0
(Male: 1)	(0.00307)	(0.00300)	(.)	(0.00307)	(0.00300)	(.)
STEM			0		0.0184***	0
			(.)		(0.00427)	(.)
AfterMeetingMobile*			0.0307***			
STEM			(0.00719)			
STEM*Log_StkMobSciEncou					-0.0201***	0.0289***
					(0.00452)	(0.00585)
Log AvCits lag	0.146***	0.147***	0.0296***	0.146***	0.147***	0.0170***
	(0.00232)	(0.00231)	(0.00345)	(0.00232)	(0.00232)	(0.00346)
constant	0.0784***	0.0786***	0.123***	0.111***	0.103***	0.120***
	(0.00556)	(0.00546)	(0.00273)	(0.00322)	(0.00388)	(0.00269)
Field FE	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No
Individual FE	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
N	66683	66683	66637	66683	66683	66637
R ²	0.394	0.392	0.630	0.394	0.393	0.633

Table 3B. Average foreign publication, panel (Brazil)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	<i>log_AvgFRG</i> <i>Npublication</i>	<i>log_AvgFR</i> <i>GNpublicat</i> <i>ion</i>	<i>log_AvgFR</i> <i>GNpublicat</i> <i>ion</i>	<i>log_AvgFR</i> <i>GNpublicat</i> <i>ion</i>	<i>log_AvgFR</i> <i>GNpublicat</i> <i>ion</i>	<i>log_AvgFR</i> <i>GNpublicat</i> <i>ion</i>
AfterMeetingM obile	0.0701*** (0.00553)	0.0665*** (0.00666)	0.0682*** (0.00715)			
Log_stkMobSc ientistEnco				0.0661*** (0.00472)	0.0651*** (0.00594)	0.124*** (0.0111)
Log_stockFRG N_lag	0.200*** (0.00448)	0.203*** (0.00478)	0.126*** (0.00524)	0.194*** (0.00451)	0.197*** (0.00478)	0.111*** (0.00485)
YearsSinceFirst Pub	-0.0102*** (0.000715)	-0.0101*** (0.000777)	0.00517*** (0.000790)	-0.0106*** (0.000808)	-0.0106*** (0.000830)	0.00228 (0.00144)
Gender (Male: 1)	0.0250** (0.00762)	0.0273** (0.00819)		0.0246** (0.00757)	0.0281** (0.00854)	
STEM					-0.0271*** (0.00677)	
AfterMeeting Mobile*STEM			0.0250* (0.0116)			
STEM*Log_st kMobScientist Encou					-0.00141 (0.00717)	0.00554 (0.00930)
Log_AVG_citat ions_lag	0.0665*** (0.00571)	0.0616*** (0.00689)	-0.00112 (0.00339)	0.0385*** (0.00626)	0.0360*** (0.00620)	-0.0549*** (0.00610)
contant	0.101*** (0.00441)	0.101*** (0.00828)	0.138*** (0.00636)	0.0997*** (0.00437)	0.116*** (0.00819)	0.130*** (0.00766)
Field FE	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No
Individual FE	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
N	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551
R ²	0.356	0.354	0.567	0.362	0.360	0.573

$p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

The role of different types of mobile scientists

Finally, we separate mobile scientists by types (returnee, diaspora, and intermittent) (Tables 4A and B) for both the share (columns 1-5) and the number (6-8) of publications with foreign scientists.

In column 1, we report results without controls. In the case of Colombia, collaborating with a higher stock of diaspora mobile scientists is associated with an increase in the share of publications with foreign co-authors that is six times as large as that of increasing the stock of returnee mobile scientists; and three times as large as that of increasing the stock of returnee mobile scientists. Indeed, when we add controls and discipline fixed effects (cols 2 and 3), we find that for the Colombian case, an increase in the number of collaborations with returnees is not associated with a significant increase in the portfolio of publications with foreign co-authors for non-mobile scientists. Similar results are found in the Brazilian case, where both diaspora and intermittent mobile scientists have a three times higher positive correlation with the share of publications with foreign co-authors than increasing the stock of returnee mobile scientists (column 1). In the Brazilian case there is less difference between the intermittent and the diaspora scientists in their role of connecting Brazilian non-mobile scientists with the rest of the world.

In column 4, we see that the large difference of the role of different types of mobile scientists in Colombia arises partly in STEM. For all non-STEM non-mobile scientists, the correlation between co-authoring with returnees and the share of publications with foreign coauthors is positive and significant even when controlling for observable features. However, for STEM scientists collaborating with mobile returnees it is negative.

Because STEM non-mobile scientists are more likely to co-author with foreign scientists than SSH scientists, this result suggests that, in Colombia, returnees substitute for foreign scientists: non-mobile STEM scientists collaborate with either returnees, or with foreign co-authors, but not with both. Once more, results are different with individual fixed effects, suggesting a positive association for all scientists, when assessing the role of returnees over their careers. In the Brazilian case (col 2), we also find that an increase in the stock of returnees is not correlated with the share of foreign publications. We find no differences between STEM and SSH.

Collaborating with Colombian scientists that do not come back (diaspora) or that are intermittent abroad is instead associated with an increased share of publications with foreign co-authors for all scientists. Results are similar for the number of publications with a foreign scientist (cols 6-8) and for the Brazilian case. As already noted, in Brazil the share of foreign collaboration is not related to the number of collaborations with unique mobile scientists, because the number of collaborations with foreign and national scientists increase at the same rate. But the number of publications with for each scientist increases almost twice as much when non-mobile scientists also collaborate with diaspora and intermittent than when they collaborate with returnees.

Table 4A. Average share of foreign publication (by different mobility categories), panel (Colombia)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	<i>Avgshare FRGNpub</i>	<i>Avgshare FRGNpub</i>	<i>Avgshare FRGNpub</i>	<i>Avgshare FRGNpub</i>	<i>Avgshare FRGNpub</i>	<i>log_Avg FRGNpub</i>	<i>log_Avg FRGNpub</i>	<i>log_Avg FRGNpub</i>
log_stkRTRN	0.0314*** (0.00231)	-0.00172 (0.00211)	-0.00347 (0.00212)	0.0158*** (0.00322)	0.0337*** (0.00483)	0.0214*** (0.00319)	0.0353*** (0.00485)	0.0596*** (0.00719)
log_stkDiaspl	0.197*** (0.00823)	0.0570*** (0.00716)	0.0574*** (0.00716)	0.0621*** (0.0118)	0.0649*** (0.0145)	0.0801*** (0.0108)	0.0615*** (0.0178)	0.0498* (0.0215)
log_stkInterml	0.0962*** (0.00231)	0.0183*** (0.00214)	0.0169*** (0.00215)	0.0262*** (0.00327)	0.0468*** (0.00497)	0.0423*** (0.00324)	0.0517*** (0.00492)	0.0913*** (0.00740)
Log_AvCits_lag		0.0385*** (0.00153)	0.0374*** (0.00154)	0.0382*** (0.00154)	-0.0427*** (0.00234)	0.145*** (0.00232)	0.146*** (0.00232)	0.0136*** (0.00348)
Log		0.117***	0.117***	0.116***	0.0820***	0.171***	0.170***	0.119***
StkFRGN_lag		(0.00114)	(0.00115)	(0.00114)	(0.00187)	(0.00173)	(0.00172)	(0.00279)
YrsSinceFirstPub		-0.00627*** (0.000220)	-0.00614*** (0.000220)	-0.00612*** (0.000220)	0.00508*** (0.000287)	-0.0114*** (0.000332)	-0.0115*** (0.000332)	0.00247*** (0.000426)
Gender (Male: 1)		0.0117*** (0.00200)	0.0120*** (0.00204)	0.0108*** (0.00199)	0 (.)	0.0304*** (0.00307)	0.0313*** (0.00300)	0 (.)
STEM				0.0351*** (0.00267)	0 (.)		0.0204*** (0.00403)	0 (.)
STEM* c.log_stkRTRN				-0.0312***	-0.0110		-0.0218***	0.00704
STEM* c.log_stkDiaspl				(0.00413)	(0.00631)		(0.00622)	(0.00938)
STEM* c.log_stkInterml				-0.00777	-0.0278		0.0235	0.0270
				(0.0148)	(0.0182)		(0.0222)	(0.0270)
				-0.0145***	-0.00252		-0.0172**	0.0261**
				(0.00413)	(0.00639)		(0.00622)	(0.00950)
cons	0.200*** (0.00146)	0.115*** (0.00210)	0.115*** (0.00211)	0.0969*** (0.00251)	0.106*** (0.00178)	0.116*** (0.00318)	0.106*** (0.00378)	0.132*** (0.00265)
Field FE	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No
Individual FE	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
N	72548	66683	66683	66683	66637	66683	66683	66637
R ²	0.052	0.293	0.296	0.295	0.562	0.395	0.394	0.633

$p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Table 4B. Average share of foreign publication (by different mobility categories), panel (Brazil)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	<i>AvgshareFRG Npub</i>	<i>AvgshareFRG Npub</i>	<i>AvgshareFRG Npub</i>	<i>AvgshareFRG Npub</i>	<i>AvgshareFRG Npub</i>	<i>log_AvgFRGNpub lication</i>	<i>log_AvgFRGNpu bication</i>	<i>log_AvgFRGNpub lication</i>
log_stkRTR	0.0179** (0.00488)	0.000926 (0.00219)	-0.000578 (0.00165)	0.00515 (0.00301)	0.00501 (0.00494)	0.0573*** (0.00780)	0.0445*** (0.00383)	0.0572*** (0.00825)
log_stkDiasp	0.0845*** (0.00639)	0.0286*** (0.00467)	0.0294*** (0.00458)	0.0292 (0.0187)	0.0352 (0.0222)	0.0792*** (0.0149)	0.0707** (0.0210)	0.0781*** (0.0187)
log_stkInter m	0.0512*** (0.00330)	0.0137*** (0.00216)	0.0124*** (0.00245)	0.00599 (0.00504)	0.0157* (0.00653)	0.119*** (0.0104)	0.0608*** (0.00629)	0.114*** (0.0110)
Log_AvCit_l a		-0.0164*** (0.00213)	-0.0164*** (0.00184)	-0.0178*** (0.00150)	-0.0497*** (0.00241)	-0.0581*** (0.00561)	0.0334*** (0.00625)	-0.0589*** (0.00592)
Log_ StkFRGN_la		0.0984*** (0.00224)	0.0980*** (0.00232)	0.0987*** (0.00237)	0.0508*** (0.00204)	0.110*** (0.00473)	0.195*** (0.00479)	0.110*** (0.00488)
YrsSinFirstP u		-0.00570*** (0.000285)	-0.00562*** (0.000323)	-0.00556*** (0.000320)	0.00376*** (0.000401)	0.00274 (0.00144)	-0.0107*** (0.000830)	0.00276 (0.00145)
Gender (Male:1)		0.00890** (0.00255)	0.00502 (0.00255)	0.00829** (0.00221)			0.0269** (0.00846)	
STEM				0.0117* (0.00413)			-0.0253** (0.00651)	
STEM*RTR				-0.00497 (0.00401)	-0.00805 (0.00617)		-0.00170 (0.00637)	0.000451 (0.0145)
STEM* c.log_stkDia				0.000658 (0.0188)	-0.00555 (0.0231)		0.0301 (0.0273)	0.00166 (0.0267)
STEM* c.log_stkIntr				0.00713 (0.00482)	0.00906 (0.00605)		-0.00207 (0.00823)	0.00630 (0.00922)
cons	0.182*** (0.00559)	0.128*** (0.00378)	0.132*** (0.00233)	0.122*** (0.00383)	0.141*** (0.00191)	0.139*** (0.00800)	0.121*** (0.00761)	0.139*** (0.00837)
Field FE	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No
IndividualFE	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
N	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551	862551
R ²	0.061	0.191	0.193	0.192	0.404	0.574	0.362	0.574

$p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Event studies results

In this section, we present the results of the difference in differences event study, separately for Colombia and Brazil. Each figure has four panels for non-mobile scientists who co-authored with: 1) any number of unique mobile scientists; 2) one unique mobile scientist; 3) two unique mobile scientists; and 4) three unique mobile scientists.

Figures 1 and 2 report the estimated effect of co-authoring with mobile scientists on the number of publications co-authored with foreign scientists for the full sample of non-mobile Colombian and Brazilian scientists, respectively.

First, in the five years before co-authoring with a mobile, treated and non-treated non-mobile scientists do not differ significantly in the number of papers they co-authored with foreign scientists, regardless of the number of unique mobile co-authors (panels 1-4).

Second, when considering any number of unique mobile co-authors (Figures 1 and 2 of panel 1), we observe that after the first co-authorship with a mobile scientist, non-mobile scientists co-author significantly more papers with foreign scientists than the control group of non-mobile scientists that never co-author with a mobile scientist.

Third, the difference is always largest in the year of first co-authorship with the mobile scientist. In all scenarios, an average Colombian non-mobile scientist, publishes approximately 20% more papers co-authored with a foreign scientist than a Colombian non-mobile scientist who has never co-authored with a mobile. In Brazil the difference can be as high as 28%. This is a large effect.

Fourth, in panel 1 there is a significant drop in the probability of foreign collaboration from year zero (the year of first collaboration with a mobile) and year 1 (the first year after). When we consider publishing with any number of mobile co-authors (panel (1)), the difference between treated and non-treated drops to around 10% in the first year after co-authoring. This suggests that the mechanism connecting non-mobile to foreign scientists is a joint publication with non-mobile, mobile, and foreign co-authors.

Unfortunately, this ‘mechanical’ effect tends not to be sustained through time, i.e. non-mobile Colombian and Brazilian scientists do not remain connected to the foreign scientists more than their untreated peers beyond that first co-authorship that involved also the mobile scientists. We observe this in Figures 1 and 2, panels (2-4). Colombian and Brazilian non-mobile scientists who co-author with only one or two unique mobile scientists are not more likely to co-author with foreign scientists in the following years than their untreated peers. Only scientists who co-author with at least three mobile scientists (in one or multiple years) still see a positive effect after two or three years. But this effect is because in each of these three years they have a higher probability to co-publish with the foreign co-authors and the mobile, rather than independently. In other words, non-mobile scientists, on average, need to be re-connected every time to foreign scientists (by a mobile colleague) to continue collaborating with foreigners.

Fourth, the event study results confirm that increasing the number of unique mobile co-authors positively affects the number of publications co-authored with foreign scientists, as discussed in the OLS regressions (Tables 3A and 3B). However, they also qualify the OLS results, showing that most of that effect is explained by including non-mobile scientists in publications that the mobile co-authors with the foreign scientists. While that may have other positive impacts, we find weak evidence that it helps establish long-lasting links between non-mobile Colombian or Brazilian scientists and foreign scientists.

In general, these results demonstrate that interacting with several mobile scientists can benefit non-mobile scientists in expanding their portfolio of foreign collaborations: as non-mobile scientists diversify their network of mobile scientists, the number of foreign publications increases. Nonetheless, although we find the role played by mobile scientists in leveraging the home scientists’ internationalization process, it is unclear how long the effect of collaborating with a mobile last. Understanding the impact length of each interaction in future research is crucial.

Figure 1. Number of papers with foreign co-authors per year in log (Colombia)

Figure 2. Number of papers with foreign co-authors per year in log (Brazil).

We next examine whether these effects change for different groups of non-mobile and mobile scientists.

We first split non-mobile scientists between STEM and SSH. Figures 3 and 4 compare results for both subsamples for Colombia and Brazil respectively.

In the case of Brazil, we observe no difference between the two disciplinary groups or with respect to the average effects in Figure 4. This is consistent with the OLS results that showed no significant difference in the role of mobile scientists between STEM and SSH non-mobile scientists.

In the case of Colombia, the difference in differences estimates do not confirm the OLS results that SSH non-mobile scientists publish more with foreign scientists than STEMs if they also co-author with mobile scientists. We almost see the opposite results, especially when they co-author with only one or two unique mobile scientists. In neither case there is a significant persistent effect in the years following the ‘mechanical’ increases in publications with foreign co-authors in the year in which non-mobile scientists co-authors with the mobile ones. But while STEM non-mobile scientists are always more likely to publish more with foreign scientists in the five years after co-authoring with a mobile scientist, SSH non-mobiles are not. Combined with the OLS evidence this suggests that SSH non-mobile scientist gain more from an increased number of mobile co-authors, precisely because the effect is less long-lasting. For a given number of mobile co-authors, STEM gain more in terms of number of publications with foreign scientists.

Next, we split mobile scientists into returnees, and intermittent plus diaspora. We study the heterogenous effect of co-authoring with the two different groups of mobile scientists on co-authoring with foreign scientists. Figures 5 and 6 compare results for Colombia and Brazil, respectively.

In the case of Colombia (Figure 5), although the smaller sample size increase the error bars, the impact of diaspora and intermittent lasts longer than that of returnees. For instance, when considering any number of collaborations with unique mobile scientists, although always positive, the difference in the number of co-authors publications with foreign scientists is never significantly different from zero in each of the years after the collaboration with the mobile. Point estimates are larger in the case of diaspora and intermittent, and the difference is significant in most of the five years following the collaborations with the mobile scientists.

In the case of Brazil (Figure 6), the difference in the impact of the two groups of mobile scientists on non-mobile scientists' international collaborations is more clearly visible. Point estimates are in general higher for diaspora and intermittent (top panels) than for returnees (bottom panel). Collaboration with diaspora and intermittent has also a more persistent effect than collaborations with returnees. When a non-mobile scientist co-authors with several unique mobile scientists who work abroad, they publish more with foreign scientists also in the five years following the first collaboration. When a non-mobile scientist co-authors with several unique mobile scientist who have come back to Brazil right after the PhD, they do not establish more collaborations with foreign scientists than the control group, already two years after the collaboration with the first returnee.

Figure 3. Number of papers with foreign co-authors per year (Colombia) – STEM and SSH

Figure 4. Number of papers with foreign co-authors per year (Brazil) – STEM and SSH

Figure 5. Number of papers with foreign co-authors per year (Colombia) – Different groups of mobile scientists

Figure 6. Number of papers with foreign co-authors per year (Brazil) – Different groups of mobile scientists

Discussion and conclusion

In this paper, we have matched unprecedented (publicly available) Brazilian and Colombian data from CVs, scholarships and publications to study a simple question for which no evidence yet exists in the literature: do mobile scientists connect non-mobile scientists from their country of origin to foreign scientists located abroad? We use panel fixed effects, controlling for a large number of observable characteristics that influence collaborations between non-mobile and foreign scientists. We use an event study approach to further isolate the mobile scientists' effect. Our results are consistent throughout: increasing the number of mobile scientists with whom non-mobile scientists interact, increases the number (and share) of publications that they co-author with foreign scientists. Results are remarkably similar for Brazil and Colombia.

First, the average non-mobile scientist from Brazil and Colombia is more likely to co-author a paper with a foreign scientist if they have published at least once with a mobile scientist. As the number of unique mobile scientists increases, the probability of co-authoring with foreign scientists also rises. Second, the number of collaborations with mobile scientists is positively associated with the share and number of publications that non-mobile scientists co-author with foreign scientists. The association is higher when controlling for individual fixed effects. On average, non-mobile scientists from Colombia and Brazil increase by 10% and 12%, the number of their foreign publications, respectively, when the number of mobile scientists with whom they collaborate doubles. STEM non-mobile scientists gain less from the interaction with mobile scientists, but only in Colombia and only when we do not control for non-observable characteristics of the non-mobile scientists. This suggests that their larger international network (in Colombia) is to some extent independent from the mobile scientists.

Coefficients are significantly larger for diaspora and intermittent scientists than they are for returnees. This result adds a contribution to the debate on brain drain: scientists who work abroad may be more beneficial to the sending country than returnees are, at least in connecting non-mobile scientists with international scientists. However, caveats apply here: as we note below, mobile scientists do not give away their networks of foreign scientists to the non-mobile scientists, rather, to a large extent the influence of mobile scientists arises from including non-mobile colleagues in their own projects with foreigners.

Our Difference-in-Difference event study identification strategy confirms the OLS results. However, they raise a concern. The effects on “internationalization” of non-mobile scientists from a small number of collaborations with mobile scientists are short lived. The benefits are strongly localized in precisely the period in which the mobile and non-mobile collaborate which suggests that what we are observing is a collaboration among mobile, non-mobile, and foreign scientists as co-authors of the same paper(s). Only for non-mobile scientists that diversify their network of mobile scientists (at least three), the impact remains statistically significant beyond the first year. The type of mobile scientist matters: non-mobile scientists who collaborate with several diaspora or intermittent scientists co-author with more foreign scientists than their non-mobile colleagues who never collaborate with several diaspora or intermittent. But non-mobile scientists who collaborate with several returnee scientists benefit only marginally in terms of “internationalization”.

Our overarching message is that mobile scientists play a relevant role in the internationalization of middle-income countries’ scientific systems. Our results contribute to the international scientific mobility literature by showing a strong pattern indicating that mobile scientists from Brazil and Colombia serve as bridges connecting between their home and foreign scientific systems. Also, adding to the brain drain versus brain circulation debate, we show that having scientists abroad may not necessarily be harmful to the sending countries. But these results need further investigation as they do not pass our identification tests. More research is needed also to study how lasting the positive effect of mobile scientists is. Our results suggest that they can be rather short term, which raises the question of whether steps can be taken to extend their effects.

Results point to some policy recommendations that, given the robustness of our results across two very dissimilar countries, are likely to be generalizable across middle income countries. First, sponsoring mobility schemes is essential as it also connects non-mobile scientists to international research. Second, conditionalities on returning to the sending country after PhD abroad may need to be more flexible, as diaspora and intermittent scientists play the main role in connecting non-mobile scientists to other countries. Nonetheless, it is also imperative that national governments engage their scientific communities abroad, to increase the role of mobile scientists. Finally, national governments can create funding lines to bring back their mobile scientists abroad for short periods. For instance, these mobile scientists could offer workshops. This paper has several limitations that need to be addressed in future research. We do not capture shorter visiting periods that scientists spend abroad. Second, we cannot identify all mobile scientists that never return to academic life in Brazil or Colombia. Third, the bibliometric data used do not capture the entire portfolio of many scientists. We miss some of their publications because many scientists publish in local journals not indexed in OpenAlex.

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